

Actinobacillus equuli: may be an Emergent Pathogen for Stud Farms

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Abstract

Actinobacillus equuli, a member of the Pasteurellaceae family, is the causative agent of frequently lethal septicemia in foals as well as other more chronic diseases including arthritis, pleuritis, pneumonia or peritonitis and occasionally infections in adult horses. It may also be isolated from primarily the upper respiratory tract and oral cavity of healthy horses. *Actinobacillus equuli* is composed of 2 subspecies namely *Actinobacillus equuli* subsp *equuli* and *Actinobacillus equuli* subsp *hemolyticus*, which are distinguished by the presence or absence of a repeats-in-toxin (RTX) toxin. Predisposing factors such as failure of passive transfer of colostral antibodies as well as concurrent pathogenic bacteria or viral infections were present in numerous cases. *Actinobacillus* spp. can be primary pathogens under the right circumstances and in the right location. A definitive diagnosis is required by isolating the bacteria in the culture.

Keywords: *Actinobacillus equuli*, equines, pneumonia, Emergent pathogen

Introduction

Actinobacillus equuli can cause deadly septicemia in foals leading to significant economic losses in the equine industry (Huang *et al.*, 2015). *A. equuli* are the most common *Actinobacillus* spp. of horses and account for most of equine infections. These are gram-negative, pleomorphic, commensal bacteria belonging to the family Pasteurellaceae. Although there are more than 22 different bacterial species in this genus, only five (*A pleuropneumoniae*, *A suis*, *A equuli*, *A lignieresii*, and *A seminis*) are regularly associated with disease in animals. This bacterium is the most common cause of embolic suppurative nephritis and septicaemia with polyarthritis in foals (sleepy foal disease), with a disease in adults including respiratory disease, cutaneous abscesses, guttural pouch infections, endometritis, pericarditis, endocarditis, peritonitis, encephalitis, arthritis, orchitis and abortion, being less frequently reported (Rycroft and Garside, 2000).

Actinobacillus equuli is composed of 2 sub species namely *Actinobacillus equuli* subsp *equuli* and *Actinobacillus equuli* subsp *hemolyticus*, which differ by the presence or absence of a repeats-in-toxin (RTX) toxin. *Actinobacillus equuli* subsp *equuli* is a normal commensal of the oral cavity and alimentary tract of adult horses and is the isolate most commonly associated with neonatal septicemia (sleepy foal disease), as well as respiratory infections in foals and adult horses. *Actinobacillus equuli* subsp *hemolyticus* is a normal inhabitant of the respiratory tract and is commonly isolated from tracheal wash fluids. However, this sub species is more commonly associated with non-respiratory infections in adult horses.

Actinobacillus equuli subsp *hemolyticus* produces a repeats-in-toxin (RTX) toxin termed Aqx, similar to the leukotoxins of *Pasteurella haemolytica*. Many RTX toxins are host specific and the pathogenesis of these bacteria is related to the RTX toxic activity (Benavente and Fuentealba, 2012).

In a recent retrospective study of actinobacillosis cases in equine, *A. equuli* subspecies *haemolyticus* was most commonly isolated from clinical cases of septicemia and respiratory disease, suggesting that this subspecies is more virulent than its sister subspecies (Layman *et al.*, 2014). The pathogenesis of *A. equuli*-induced respiratory disorders in horses resembles that of other commensal bacteria, e.g. *Streptococcus equi* subsp *zooepidemicus* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Epidemiology

Habitat

- Actinobacilli are commensal parasites on mucous membranes.
- *Actinobacillus equuli* is a common inhabitant of the equine upper respiratory tract and oral cavity.
- Prevalence in healthy horses in other studies ranges from 12-88%.

Transmission

- *Actinobacillus equuli* infection in foals may be acquired, probably from the normal flora of the dam, via a contaminated umbilicus, or by inhalation or ingestion. Phenotypically and genotypically identical strains have been isolated from mares and their foals.
- Clinical disease in adult horses is probably caused by exposure to non-commensal strains.

Pathogenesis

In foals, predisposing factors to the development of disease are failure of passive transfer of maternal antibodies, unsanitary conditions in the foaling area and concurrent immunosuppressive conditions. Infection in foals is acquired *in utero*, during parturition, or shortly after birth as an umbilical infection or less commonly from gastrointestinal (ingestion) or respiratory (inhalation) infections. Disease

presentation is often peracute with death at birth or within the 1st few days due to fulminant septicemia. These neonatal septicemic infections are considered to be primary infections in most instances.

Foals afflicted by the peracute disease are born weak, refuse to suck, or do so sluggishly, and are feverish, dull, and lethargic. They stand with heads hanging and ears drooping before they become recumbent and die. They seldom live for more than 24 hours.

In adult horses, actinobacillosis is rare and usually acts as a secondary bacterial infection complicating some other primary condition, usually some other concurrent pathogenic bacteria or viral infection, but under the right circumstances, *Actinobacillus* spp can be primary pathogens. Infection in adult horses is generally more localized and includes cutaneous abscesses, guttural pouch infections, endometritis, pericarditis, endocarditis, peritonitis, encephalitis, arthritis, orchitis and abortion. The syndromes of acute peritonitis, encephalitis and fatal pulmonary hemorrhage with pneumonia due to endothelial damage caused by bacterial toxins, have been more recently described. In addition, it has been documented that the same mare may abort in successive pregnancies. Rare cases of septicemia associated with both *Actinobacillus equuli* subsp *equuli* and *Actinobacillus equuli* subsp *hemolyticus*, have been documented.

Diagnosis

Molecular techniques such as PCR and ELISA have also been developed that detect the presence of the organism in tissue samples. Both in foals and adult horses, several other bacteria can cause the same clinical disease syndromes as *A. equuli*, so a definitive diagnosis is important, which requires isolating the bacteria in culture.

- In live foals, the preferred sample is blood for blood culture collected directly into blood culture bottles.
- In dead foals at postmortem kidneys and lungs are the preferred tissues, either fresh biopsies or charcoal swabs.
- In adult horses, the primary target organ of the disease syndrome is sampled.

Prevention and Control

Infected horses may be treated with various antibiotics including streptomycin, tetracycline, ampicillin and trimethoprim – sulfonamide, with antibiotic selection being based on the antibiotic sensitivity profile, nature of the infection and the ability of the antibiotic to achieve therapeutic concentrations at the site of infection.

Neonatal septicemia (sleepy foal disease) is best prevented through employing a combination of strict environmental hygiene, practicing of foaling camp rotation, ensuring intake of colostrum as soon

after birth as possible, umbilical disinfection and immediate removal of the expelled placenta and soiled bedding post foaling. Remember, the mare's reproductive tract and fetal membranes are the primary source of bacteria for the foal, and therefore another practical prevention measure where an infection is suspected, is the installation of bovine antibiotic mastitis remedies (containing tetracycline or penicillin), into the mare's birth canal shortly before foaling.

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